

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE USE OF COMPUTER SIMULATION IN THE STUDY OF THE CONDITION OF SUPPORTING TEETH

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Abstract

A relationship between the degree of activity zones of tension, the direction of the applied load and the condition of the bone tissue of the alveolar process. Calculated data confirming the absolute values of the indicators of stresses and displacements dentition segment elements. The magnitude of alternating stress and displacement elements in various areas of human dentoalveolar apparatus depends on the strength and direction of load, as well as the bone density of alveolar bone.

Keywords: computer analysis, physiological mobility, abutment teeth.

Periodontal diseases occupy one of the leading places among the various forms of pathologies of the maxillofacial region. A large number of studies [1, 2, 3, 4, 5] deeply consider the physiological, anatomical-histological, pathoanatomical, biological and biochemical aspects of diseases. Biomechanical analysis is most often carried out very superficially, without the involvement of modern technologies and methods [6].

Dental scientists interpret the problems of biomechanics in dentistry very narrowly [5], although only biomechanical analysis using modern methods of mathematical modeling [6,8] allows a deeper study of the work of any biological system. The introduction of computer technology is often the only way to fully and in-depth study of biomechanical criteria. Computer-aided design is always preferred over clinical model simulation. Under the influence of forces arising in the dentoalveolar system during function, there is a deformation of all periodontal tissue elements: tooth, alveolar bone and gums with periosteum, as well as the ligamentous apparatus - periodontium [1, 2, 3, 4]. The resulting stress at certain values, duration and nature of the action can lead to a restructuring of the bone tissue and, as a result, contribute to the emergence of various pathological changes. A solid analysis at the current level of development of computer technology makes it possible to study the state of the "tooth-periodontium" biosystem both in normal conditions and in any form and degree of pathology. Such an analysis can be carried out more easily and effectively using finite element modeling (FEM) [6,8]. Usually, at the first stage, studies are carried out on the stress-strain state (SSS) of any structure in the norm, and then with various pathologies, methods of orthopedic treatment, various types of prosthesis designs, etc.

In computer design, two types of models are used to study biomechanical properties: flat and volumetric. Qualitative changes can be studied using a simpler planar model, and then a 3D model can be built to obtain accurate digital data.

This work is devoted to the analysis of the stress-strain state of the periodontium, depending on the type and degree of atrophy of the bone tissue of the alveolar process.

When analyzing SSS, stress and displacement (following strain) are determined at all points of the system under study. In the available dental literature, much more attention is paid to the issues of mobility (determination of movements) of the tooth than to the issues of strength [3, 4, 5, 9].

Distinguish between physiological and pathological tooth mobility. Physiological mobility is natural and may not always be visible to the naked eye. Its existence is confirmed with the help of special equipment, as well as indirect signs in the form of erasure of contact points and the appearance of contact planes with age.

Pathological mobility is characterized by a noticeable displacement (in size and direction) of the teeth at low loads. The degree of pathological tooth mobility depends on the severity of the damage to the musculoskeletal apparatus of the tooth and the nature of the course of the inflammatory-destructive process in the periodontium. Pathological tooth mobility is pronounced with a vertical form of resorption of the bone tissue of the alveolar process [1]

Many authors [1, 3, 5] distinguish three degrees of tooth mobility. structure of bone tissue and, as a result, contribute to the emergence of various pathological changes. A solid analysis at the current level of development of computer technology makes it possible to study the state of the "tooth-periodontium" biosystem both in normal conditions and in any form and degree of pathology. Such an analysis can be carried out more easily and effectively using finite element modeling (FEM) [6,8]. Usually, at the first stage, studies are carried out on the stress-strain state (SSS) of any structure in the norm, and then with various pathologies, methods of orthopedic treatment, various types of prosthesis designs, etc.

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Many authors [1, 3, 5] distinguish three degrees of tooth mobility. However, in the manual edited by V.N. Kopeikin [4], four measures of mobility are proposed: I - mobility in one or one direction - vestibular, oral, medial or distal; II - in two directions (according to [1] both in the vestibulo-oral and sagittal directions); III - in the vestibulo-oral and medio-distal; IV - in all directions, including vertical.

From the point of view of mechanics, one can imagine a tooth as a solid body, fixed in periodontal space, having six degrees of freedom: three translational and

three rotational about three orthogonal axes. The mobility of a tooth as a solid body is determined by the possible total displacements relative to these axes. In addition, as an elastic body, the tooth has an infinite number of degrees of freedom.

The most probable in this case are tensile or compression deformations along the longitudinal axis of the tooth, rotation around the longitudinal axis, as well as bending in the vestibulo-oral or mediobuccal directions. Knowing the conditions for fixing an elastic body and deforming loads in different directions, we can determine the elastic displacements of all points of the tooth section. Specifically, all these movements of the tooth as both a rigid and elastic body determine its total movements, which in dentistry are commonly referred to as tooth mobility. canine areas. The tooth profile was made according to Harty [11], and the contours of the segment were taken according to V.N. Kopeikin[4]. The model contains the main structural components of the FFS: the tooth, including the crown (enamel), dentin, tooth neck and root (cement), periodontal fissure, inner and outer cortical plates of the dental alveolus, and spongy substance of the jawbone.

The main mechanical characteristics, according to the data of [10], are assigned to the main structural components of the model, given in Table 1.

Элемент модели	E МПа	μ	Количество элементов	$\sigma_{в.р}$ МПа	$\sigma_{в.с}$ МПа
Эмаль	$4 \cdot 10^4$	0,3	369	1,1-34	130-380
Дентин	$1,56 \cdot 10^3$	0,3	709	2 -104	230-310
Компактная кость	$1,37 \cdot 10^4$	0,3	722	40-50	50-400
Губчатая кость	$6,89 \cdot 10^3$	0,3	897	10-20	26-160
Периодонт	50,0	0,45	76	3,8	

In table. 1 marked: E - modulus of elasticity of bone tissue; μ is Poisson's ratio; $\sigma_{в.р}$ and $\sigma_{в.с}$ - tensile and compressive strength, respectively. The tensile strengths are given in the table as a reference to enable comparison of the resulting effective stress with the maximum allowable (destructive). The mechanical characteristics of periodontal tissues given in Table 1 reflect only the elastic (linear) properties of bone and soft tissues. At the same time, it is quite obvious [7,10] that bone and especially soft tissues have significant plasticity, that is, non-linearity. Modern programs that implement the finite element method (FEM) make it possible to take into account any type of nonlinearity.

Therefore, the issue of building an appropriate model should be considered taking into account reliable initial data on the elasticity of the periodontium. When analyzing a linear model, which is a more rigid system than a real biosystem, it must be taken into account that the tooth movements obtained with its help will be less, and the stress will be greater by the difference between the introduced additional mechanical characteristics and the real ones. Since a flat model, compared to a volumetric (three-dimensional), in principle it cannot be more accurate, when working out the model, special attention was paid to the adequacy of the developed model with the real structure of the jaw, not only qualitatively, but also quantitatively, ensuring the comparability of the obtained numerical results. with those

known in the literature. To ensure a true interaction between the tooth root and the periodontal layers surrounding it, the width of the root was determined by the equality of the volumes of the real tooth root and the complexity of the structure and function of the periodontium, which absorbs mechanical energy and redistributes it to the alveolar bone tissue, in our opinion, has not yet been adequately reflected in scientific literature. When working out the parameters of this most important component of the HFJ, we used the usual periodontal model with elastic properties according to U. Mandel et al. [12]. The described basic model was modernized, i.e. Its geometry was rebuilt depending on the type and degree of vertical and horizontal resorption of the alveolar bone. The load was taken according to Rus equal to 150 N, that is, the upper limit of the force of solid food that occurs during chewing in the canine area. The force, according to the scheme (Fig. 83 of [4]), is applied at a point slightly below the cutting edge of the tooth at an angle of 45° relative to the vertical.

The program, with which the model is built and analyzed, records in the protocol the solution of the problem of moving each node along three coordinate axes, normal and tangential along the axes, the main stress and the von Mises stress at each nodal point and inside each element. The von Mises voltage is calculated using the usual formula.

$$\sigma_M = \sqrt{0,5[(\sigma_x - \sigma_y)^2 + (\sigma_y - \sigma_z)^2 + (\sigma_z - \sigma_x)^2] + 6(\tau_{xy}^2 + \tau_{yz}^2 + \tau_{zx}^2)}$$

Below, we analyze the developed flat model, so this formula will be greatly simplified, since all components of the stress state containing the index z will be equal to zero. In all cases, the stress concentration that occurs at the point of application of a concentrated force, according to the Saint-Venant principle, was not taken into account, since this issue requires a separate

study using a model adequate to such a formulation of the problem. In the first row of the table. 2, the maximum values of the quantities that will be used in the analysis are placed: total displacements DR, tooth compliance, and normal stress σ_y in various structural components of the system

№ моделі	Вертик.резорб./ Гориз.резорб.	Перемещение DR, мм	Податливость δ мм/Н	Напряжение σ_y , МПа		
				Коронка	Шейка	Компактная кость
1	25%/0	0,88	0,0059	11,84 - 18,15	44,26 - 56,77	20,69 - 21,08
2	50%/0	2,224	0,0148	9,64 - 19,22	69,97 - 74,07	12,89 - 12,15
3	75%/0	11,19	0,0746	11,89 - 16,6	168,13 - 208,03	16,86 - 16,62
4	50%/0,5мм	3,064	0,0204	11,83 - 19,2	69,57 - 69,92	16,72 - 19,77
5	50%/0,75мм	3,57	0,0238	13,32 - 19,2	69,18 - 71,96	15,69 - 18,26
6	50%/0,5мм 1,25E	3,057	0,0204	11,83 - 18,18	69,58 - 69,9	17,64 - 19,06
7	50%/0,5мм 0,75E	3,076	0,0205	11,83 - 19,22	69,56 - 69,95	16,09 - 16,25
8	50% F гориз.	3,218	0, 21	23,95 - 24,3	111,42 - 100,85	21,93 - 22,8

Usually [1, 13] the influence of the magnitude of alveolar resorption on the decrease in periodontal endurance is estimated as a percentage. In our opinion, this indicator is not very convenient and informative. In the theory of strength, a relative indicator is widely used - the safety factor (or a safety factor close to it in meaning), which can practically be expressed as the ratio of two quantities included in inequality (1), i.e.

$$n = \frac{\sigma_u}{\sigma}$$

At the same time, it is not specified at all in relation to which structural components of the periodontium the decrease in endurance is estimated. Based on this, further (taking into account the fact that the destructive stress - the strength limits of bone tissues (see

Table 1), according to the literature data, lie in a wide range), we suggest that the resulting stress in all structural components of the periodontium under a load equal to the maximum endurance periodontium are destructive. Thus, we get a database of the bearing capacity of a healthy periodontium for comparison.

After these preparatory remarks and suggestions, we proceed to a more detailed analysis of periodontal endurance (bearing capacity) depending on the type and degree of alveolar bone resorption.

In the third, fourth and fifth rows of the shows the results of the analysis of BAT periodontitis tissues with vertical resorption of bone tissue, visually equal to 25%, 50% and 75%. For the first time, it is important to note the recommended reserve ratio for the stated resorption rates. (tabl 4)

Степень резорбції	0	25%	50%	75%
Розтягнута зона	2,4	1,38	0,87	0,360
краткая зона	2,4	1,51	1,12	0,398

At 50% of the vertical resorption reserve, the vitreous body of the tooth is practically elastic - the reserve coefficient is close to unity. Periodontal stability is estimated at 25%, 50% and 75%, respectively, at 1.88; 4.72 and 23.8 times. It is especially evident that the degree of overload of the alveolar bone does not increase so significantly, and in some cases even decreases. This is explained, from our point of view, as follows. The load (external force) is non-conservative, that is, it rotates as the bending deformation of the tooth grows so that it increasingly acts strictly along the axis of the tooth. All structural components of the denoalveolar segment increasingly begin to work only in

compression, and this type of load, as shown above (see relation (5)), causes significantly less stress than in bending. For a comparative analysis of the influence of the direction of force on the SSS, a calculation was made for the case when the force acts strictly horizontally. The results for this case are shown in the last row of the table and in Fig. 8 They should be compared with the corresponding data in the fourth row of the table. Compliance increased 1.4 times, tension at the root tooth - 1.4.1.6 times, and the tension in the outer plate of the alveolar bone - almost 2 times. Naturally, the vertical resorption of the tooth, as well as any changes in the properties of the bone, does not occur in isolation

with inflammatory and dystrophic phenomena. In the eighth and ninth lines of Table. Figure 2 shows the results of the SSS analysis with a change in the stiffness properties of the alveolar tissues (modulus of elasticity), respectively, by 1.25 and 0.75 times, which is possible, for example, with the phenomena of osteosclerosis or osteoporosis, with vertical and horizontal resorption equal to 50% and 0.5, respectively. mm. Such changes in the stiffness properties of the alveolar bone on the SSS of the periodontium did not make significant changes. We also note that with the help of the developed model, it is possible to study the violation of the integrity of the cortical plate (and any other structural component) in the event of the occurrence of areas affected by osteoporosis.

The SSS components for this case are not given not only because of the limited size of the article, but mainly because of the many options for changing properties depending on the condition of a particular patient. Each typical case can be the subject of a separate study.

The proposed flat conventional-elemental model of the FFS fragment allows one to study in sufficient detail the SSS of the jaw segment in the area of the lower canine in various periodontal diseases - vertical, horizontal and age-related resorption of the alveolus from the standpoint of deep biomechanical analysis. Changes to the model can be made quickly, depending on the availability of new data. This allows for an individualized approach to choosing the optimal orthopedic treatment method.

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СТАН КІСТКОВОЇ ТКАНИНИ У ХВОРИХ НА ГЕНЕРАЛІЗОВАНИЙ ПАРОДОНТИТ ЗА ДАНИМИ ДЕНСИТОМЕТРИЧНОГО ОБСТЕЖЕННЯ

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THE STATE OF BONE TISSUE IN PATIENTS WITH GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS ACCORDING TO DENSITOMETRY EXAMINATION DATA

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Анотація

У статті наведено результати проведеного обстеження пацієнтів із патологією тканин пародонта: дослідження кальцій-фосфорного обміну та мінеральної щільності кісткової тканини.

Аналіз отриманих результатів показує, що у хворих на генералізований пародонтит перебіг захворювання супроводжується дисбалансом параметрів кісткового метаболізму. Проведені денситометричні